

CONTENT AND OBJECTIVES OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology,
Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

azizaturemuratova85@gmail.com

Mambetkarimova Nargiza

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Tilepova Dilfuza

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Esbosinova Shaxsanem

Student of Karakalpak State University.

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Abstract. *The main purpose of this article is to analyze the ideas based on pedagogical analysis based on practical stages of studying the social functions of the modern education system. The main essence of the modern educational program system is to analyze the importance of education in society and develop practical recommendations based on pedagogical research.*

Also, many analyses and comments are made based on the new teaching methodology of our experienced teachers.

Keywords: *Education, pedagogical research, educational methodology, pedagogical methods, educational system, pedagogical skills, innovative education.*

TA'LIM JARAYONLARINING MA'NOSI VA FUNKSIYALARI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsad hozirgi vaqtdagi zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining sotsial funksiyalarini o'rganish bo'yicha amaliy bosqichlarga asoslangan pedagogik tahlillarga asoslangan holda fikrlarni tahlil qilishdan iborat. Zamonaviy ta'lim dasturi sistemasining asosiy mohiyati ta'limning jamiyat hayotidagi ahamiyatini tahlil qilish va pedagogik tadqiqotlar asosida amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Shuningdek, tajribali o'qituvchilarimizning ta'lim berishdagi yangi metodikasi asosida ko'plab tahlillar va mulohazalar keltirib o'tilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ta'lim pedagogik tadqiqotlar, ta'lim metodikasi, pedagogik metodlar, ta'lim sistemasi, pedagogik mahorat, innovatsion ta'lim.*

Introduction

As in all aspects of the world, in the field of education, we express the opinion that globalization processes, the development of information technologies, the transformation of modern methodological programs of education through new innovative pedagogical methods, new social requirements are radically changing the form and content of the modern education system.

Today, education has become not only a process of imparting knowledge, but also a force that directly affects the economic, political, cultural and spiritual life of society as modern educational institutions based on social pedagogical research. From this point of view, the application of modern educational programs aimed at studying the main social tasks of the education system in our country in an innovative education system, as well as the analysis of their essence and development based on practical approaches to the modern educational program, is an

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urgent issue. Based on the fact that the state reforms implemented in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, in particular, the priority areas of the Law "On Education", the strategy "New Uzbekistan - New Education" are showing their effectiveness in practice, the "Concept for the Development of the Continuous Education System" sets out a number of tasks aimed at improving the quality of education in our country, strengthening the social foundations of education and an innovative approach to education. This requires further activation of the social functions of the modern education system and contributes to the development of intellectual thinking skills of teachers. The education system is a social institution that prepares a person for social life in society, forms his knowledge, skills, qualifications and worldview. The interpretation of education by Uzbek professors and teachers as "a continuous process aimed at the personal and professional development of an individual" is one of the factors determining the stages of development of education in this broad sense. In this sense, the education system is not only the main importance of individual development, but also the foundation of social progress. The modern education system is the most effective mechanism for the formation of human capital. Because through education and upbringing, qualities such as creativity, diligence, social responsibility, patriotism are formed in a person. The modern education system, in turn, involves improving this process through a methodological type of activity based on innovative technologies and pedagogical research and interactive methods based on digital tools. In recent years, many studies have been conducted by Uzbek scientists on the modernization of education, the introduction of new educational system programs and innovative approaches to education, and based on the results of many studies, modern pedagogical activity is studied from a sociological perspective. Education is also called the "central link of the social system" and directly connects it with the spiritual stability of society.

In modern pedagogical research, special attention should be paid to the issues of person-centered education, a competency-based approach, digital pedagogy, ecological and inclusive education. To study the collaborative formation of students, it is necessary to increase their interest and interest in science. In the modern educational process, it is necessary to use methods that use all existing organizational forms of teaching. Only in the context of the teacher's joint work with the student are cooperative relationships studied that have a specific personal meaning for each individual. They are manifested in specific relationships, as well as in the interaction of the teacher and students, in the coordination of speech acts.

It should be noted that if the teacher promotes real cooperation with students, then he sets a clear goal for the lesson, which corresponds to the real goals of the communication being produced. The student is helped in the process of implementing not only the main goal of the lesson, but also a possible way to achieve it. The level of success in education is associated not only with the joint coordination of the work of the teacher and the student, but also with the interaction of their personalities, as well as with the mutual understanding that is formed between them. That is why, even if the teacher's professional training is acceptable, the effectiveness of teaching at the methodological level, as well as the ability to purposefully plan his actions, may decrease due to non-cooperative relationships. The state of formation in cooperation develops mainly among a certain group of students (collective student group). If we talk about direct pedagogical, educational cooperation in a general sense, we should not forget that there are three

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main factors that are formed in the process of interaction between the teacher and the student, the interaction of students with each other. The modern model of pedagogical education provides information about the manifestation of educational technology not only in the process of joint activity, but also in the interaction of teachers in the system of interdisciplinary relations. The main idea of this technology is to create conditions for joint active educational activities of students in various educational settings. These approaches serve to form the educational process as a basic system focused on humane, flexible and socially active. A methodology based on pedagogical analysis is a key factor determining the quality of modern education.

Modern educational methodology should be aimed at mutual cooperation between the student and the teacher (collaborative learning), the development of independent thinking, solving problem situations and the formation of creative thinking. Currently, interactive methods (pedagogical methods, brainstorming, debate, project-based learning systems) are widely used in the education system. All this increases the social significance of the educational process. It can also be defined as a type of collaborative formation carried out by students together.

Collaborative learning has a number of important advantages over traditional teaching methods. The joint activities of children develop skills such as communication, listening, expressing their point of view, and freely expressing their opinions. With a properly structured lesson, all students are involved in learning, and the cognitive activity of children included in such groups is activated. In the modern pedagogical world, it is customary to distinguish a number of models of classes, each of which is selected and modified depending on the ultimate goal of the lesson. These can be classes in which children are divided into large or small groups, in which children receive the same or different tasks. They use pedagogical methods based on model mechanisms, in which game elements are used or constructive dialogue is conducted with a specialist in the subject being studied. In the conditions of the modern globalizing world, it is impossible to remain at the usual levels of education, it is necessary to change the existing system in order to most effectively prepare children for the needs of the future, for independent life. The method of joint education allows the child to develop not only intelligence and a desire to learn the world around him. It also forms responsibility for peers, respect for other people's opinions, the desire for success, and creative activity. The most important social function of education is the formation of a human personality. A person acquires his social position in his life through education. Education not only enriches a person with knowledge, but also increases social responsibility, preserves morality, becomes cultured, and increases the ability to communicate.

The education system is a modern stage of education that strengthens ties between social groups, uniting them around a single goal. This is called an innovative education system based on a social integration system. Today, in the education system of Uzbekistan, such ideas as ensuring gender equality, developing inclusive education, and making socially just decisions in the field of pedagogy are gaining momentum. This helps to bring the social functions of education to a new level and develop a modern education system. Through a teaching system based on pedagogical methods, students learn to freely express their opinions, the main factors of managing relationships in a team, and solve problems in the social environment. Therefore, the social outcome of the methods of pedagogical educational programs of the modern education system is of primary importance in the development of civic engagement, culture, tolerance, and humanity.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that the modern education system has a profound impact on all aspects of social life. Its social tasks open up new opportunities for the formation of skills for the comprehensive development of the individual, serve to ensure social integration, spiritual renewal and economic stability in education. The education system is one of the social connecting factors between the individual and society. Pedagogical skills and innovative methods help increase the social effectiveness of education. The main social task of education is to form a person as a socially mature, spiritually rich and ready to actively participate in education.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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